

Original Research

Information and support needs of childhood, adolescent, and young adult cancer survivors (CAYACS) across Europe and associations with patient activation and health-related quality of life: Results from the e-QuoL project

Anne Maas^a, Valeriia Balaeva^a, Maëlle de Ville de Goyet^b, Jelica Predojevic^c, Jelena Roganovic^d, Charlotte Demoor-Goldschmidt^{e,f,g}, Amandine Bertrand^h, Päivi Lähteenmäki^{g,i}, Mira Pomrénⁱ, Eugenie Werbenko^j, Beate Timmermann^{j,k}, Magdalena Balcerek^l, Miklós Garami^m, Zsuzsanna Jakab^m, Monica Muracaⁿ, Sara Obertiⁿ, Hanne C. Lie^{g,o}, Kristen E.T. Thornton^o, Lorna Zadavec Zaletel^{p,q}, Katharina Roser^a, Anica Ilic^{a,o,1}, Gisela Michel^{a,*}

^a University of Lucerne, Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, Lucerne, Switzerland

^b Department of Paediatric Haematology-Oncology, Cliniques Universitaires Saint-Luc, Brussels, Belgium

^c Children's Hospital, University Clinical Centre of the Republic of Srpska, Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

^d Children's Hospital Zagreb, Klaićeva 16, Zagreb 10000, Croatia

^e Pediatric Oncology-Hematology-Immunology Department, University Hospital of Caen, Caen, France

^f Epidemiology of radiation, U1018 Inserm, Gustave Roussy, Villejuif, France

^g PanCare, European Network for Long-Term Follow-Up of Childhood Cancer Survivors, the Netherlands

^h Pediatric oncology unit, Leon Berard Comprehensive Cancer Center, Lyon, France

ⁱ Turku University Hospital and University of Turku, Turku, Finland

^j Westdeutsches Protonentherapiezentrum Essen (WPE) gGmbH, University Hospital Essen, Essen, Germany

^k Clinic for Particle Therapy, University Hospital Essen, Essen, Germany

^l Department of Oncology, Hepatology and Pneumology, University Hospital Leipzig and University Cancer Center Leipzig, Liebigstraße 22, Leipzig 04103, Germany

^m Hungarian National Childhood Cancer Registry, Hungarian Pediatric Oncology Network (HuPON), Pediatric Center, Semmelweis University, Budapest, Hungary

ⁿ IRCCS Istituto Giannina Gaslini, Genoa, Italy

^o Department of Behavioural Medicine, Institute of Basic Medical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway

^p Institute of Oncology Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

^q Medical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Information needs

Support needs

Childhood cancer survivors

Young adult cancer survivors

Health-related quality of life (HRQoL)

Patient activation

ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study assessed the prevalence and type of information and support needs among European childhood, adolescent, and young adult cancer survivors (CAYACS), their socio-demographic and clinical predictors, and associations with patient activation and health-related quality of life (HRQoL).

Methods: The e-QuoL Needs Study is a cross-sectional survey conducted in 15 European countries. Adult CAYACS (≥ 18 years, diagnosed before age 25 years) completed the modified Childhood Cancer Survivor Study-Needs Assessment Questionnaire (CCSS-NAQ), Patient Activation Measure® (PAM®), and PROMIS Global Health scales (HRQoL). Logistic and linear regression models were used to examine associations between socio-demographic and clinical characteristics, patient activation, and HRQoL.

Results: Overall, 571 CAYACS who completed $\geq 50\%$ of the items in at least one CCSS-NAQ domain were included (71% female; 75% in the age group 18–35 years; 47% diagnosed >10 years ago). In all domains, except spirituality, most participants (62–90%) reported at least one need, with the highest prevalence found for cancer-related health information (90%), psycho-emotional consequences (87%), and health system concerns (84%). Females, survivors residing in Eastern Europe, and those with neurocognitive late effects were most likely to report needs ($p < 0.05$). Reporting needs was associated with lower patient activation and poorer mental and physical HRQoL.

* Correspondence to: University of Lucerne, Alpenquai 4, Lucerne 6005, Switzerland.

E-mail address: gisela.michel@unilu.ch (G. Michel).

¹ Joint last authorship

Conclusions: Information and support needs remain highly prevalent among European CAYACS, even long after diagnosis. Routine assessment of individual needs and targeted information strategies tailored to survivor groups identified as having higher needs may help reduce regional inequities, improve patient activation, and optimize HRQoL.

1. Background

Survivors of childhood, adolescent, and young adult cancer (CAYACS) often continue to experience substantial information needs long after treatment [1]. These needs concern diagnosis and treatment history, late effects, fertility, lifestyle behaviors, and long-term follow-up care [1], as well as psychosocial, emotional, and practical concerns related to education, employment, and relationships [2,3]. Yet, access to comprehensive, reliable information remains inconsistent across Europe, and survivors have frequently described the absence of a central, trusted information source [4].

Information and support needs may emerge alongside the long-term consequences of cancer and its treatment. CAYACS are at risk of a range of late effects—health problems attributable to the disease itself or its treatment—including second primary neoplasms, cardiovascular disease, organ dysfunction, fatigue, and cognitive difficulties that may arise soon after treatment or decades later [5–7]. Long-term follow-up care with adequate information provision is therefore essential [8].

While these insights are valuable, important gaps in the literature remain. Most studies have been conducted in Western countries [1], while within Europe substantial disparities in survivorship care persist [9], which may lead to regional differences in meeting survivors' needs. Furthermore, some socio-demographic (e.g., female sex [10], older age [11], lower education levels [10,12]) and clinical factors (e.g., longer time since diagnosis [10,11], presence of late effects [10,13]) have been associated with unmet needs, other potential determinants—such as European region, neurocognitive late effects, follow-up care attendance—remain understudied.

Unmet needs are associated with poorer health-related quality of life (HRQoL) and psychosocial well-being [1]. A European systematic review further showed that childhood cancer survivors generally report poorer quality of life than comparison groups [14]. Moreover, CAYACS have indicated that receiving more information would help them feel empowered to take charge of their care [15]. In this context, patient activation—defined as patients' knowledge, skills, and confidence in managing their health [16]—is particularly relevant. Higher patient activation is associated with more effective self-management, greater adherence to medical advice, and better health outcomes [17,18]. These benefits are particularly important for CAYACS, who must manage potential late effects and attend regular follow-up care where such services are available. Examining how unmet needs relate to both patient activation and HRQoL is therefore essential.

To address these gaps, this study assessed (a) the prevalence of information and support needs among adult CAYACS across European regions, (b) associated socio-demographic and clinical factors, and (c) associations of needs with patient activation and HRQoL.

2. Methods

This cross-sectional study is part of the e-QuoL (Equality in Quality of Life; www.equolproject.eu) project titled “e-health tools to promote Equality in Quality of Life for childhood to young adulthood cancer patients, survivors and their families—a Pan-European project supported by the Pan-Care and HARMONIC consortia”. This European-funded initiative implements and up-scales e-health tools to improve the HRQoL of CAYACS and is conducted in close collaboration with CAYACS to support self-management of their health [19].

2.1. Sample and procedures

The e-QuoL Needs Study (eQuoL NS) surveyed CAYACS who were diagnosed with cancer before age 25 years (classified according to the International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition [ICCC–3] [20]), were aged ≥ 16 years at the time of the survey, and were no longer in treatment or living with active malignant disease. Because validated HRQoL measures differed for minors, only participants ≥ 18 years were included in these analyses. Data from participants aged 16–17 years will be analyzed separately in a later phase of the study.

Recruitment occurred in 15 European countries; the anonymous online survey was also open to participants from additional European countries. Respondents living outside Europe were excluded. No identifiable information was collected. Ethical approval was obtained where required.

Data were collected between August 8 and December 1, 2024. Detailed study procedures, and information per country, including start dates, recruitment strategies, and ethical approvals, are provided in [Appendix A](#) and [Appendix B](#), respectively.

2.2. Measurements

The study consisted of a single questionnaire administered via Qualtrics XM and available in 15 languages.

2.2.1. Information and support needs

Needs were assessed using a modified version of the Childhood Cancer Survivor Study-Needs Assessment Questionnaire (CCSS-NAQ) [21], a 164-item instrument covering 13 domains. Nine domains are part of the validated version of the instrument (psycho-emotional consequences, health system concerns, cancer-related health information, general health, survivor care and support, surveillance, coping, fiscal concerns, and relationships). Four additional domains from the original, pre-validated version (nutrition, sexuality, services, and spirituality) were also included, as these were considered potentially relevant for CAYACS. These additional items were obtained from the original authors via personal communication. Items were rated as *no need*, *need satisfied*, *low*, *moderate*, or *high need*.

2.2.2. Patient activation

Patient activation was assessed with the Patient Activation Measure® (PAM®) [22,23], a 21-item, unidimensional scale that reflects a developmental model of activation. Obtained scores range from 0 to 100 and were calculated and categorized into four progressive levels by the license holder: (1) recognizing the importance of the patient role, (2) having the confidence and knowledge to act, (3) taking action to maintain and improve health, and (4) sustaining behaviors even under stress. The PAM® has demonstrated high reliability and good psychometric properties across diverse populations, including cancer patients [22–24].

2.2.3. Mental and physical HRQoL

Mental and physical HRQoL were assessed with the PROMIS Scale v1.2 - Global Health [25], from which the Global Physical Health score, and the Global Mental Health score (each 4 items) were derived. Both scores were scaled as T-scores (mean=50, SD=10), with higher scores indicating better HRQoL. They have demonstrated good reliability and validity [25].

2.2.4. Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics

We assessed the following socio-demographic and clinical characteristics: age; gender; education level according to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) 2011 [26]; and European region, classified geographically according to the United Nations geoscheme [27] (Northern Europe [Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Ireland, Norway, Sweden, United Kingdom], Western Europe [Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Switzerland, the Netherlands], Eastern Europe [Hungary, Romania], and Southern Europe [Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Italy, Slovenia, Spain]), time since diagnosis, primary cancer diagnosis, follow-up care attendance, and presence of (neurocognitive) late effects. To ensure anonymity, the response options were aggregated into broader categories.

2.3. Analysis

All analyses were performed using Stata version 19.0. Respondents completing $\geq 50\%$ of items in at least one CCSS-NAQ domain were included.

2.3.1. Prevalence of information and support needs

For each domain, we reported the proportion of participants indicating any need (low, moderate, or high) among those who completed $\geq 50\%$ of items in that domain. Among participants who reported at least one need within a domain, we calculated the mean domain-level need. To do this, item responses were recoded as 0 =no or met (satisfied) need, 1 =low, 2 =moderate, and 3 =high need. The mean score across all completed items within a domain was subsequently calculated. Domain-level needs were categorized as no (0), low ($>0 < 1.5$), moderate ($\geq 1.5 < 2.5$), or high ($\geq 2.5 < 3$). Prevalence estimates were derived using descriptive statistics and are presented overall, by European region, and at the item level.

2.3.2. Associations between socio-demographic and clinical characteristics and information and support needs

For each domain of needs, multivariable logistic regression models were conducted with the presence of any need (yes=1 vs. no=0) as the dependent variable, and age, gender, European region, time since diagnosis, follow-up care attendance, and (neurocognitive) late effects as independent variables. Except for age and gender, these characteristics were selected because they have been understudied in previous research [1]. Given the limited number of independent variables and the large sample size, no preselection of variables was performed.

2.3.3. Patient activation and HRQoL as outcomes of information and support needs

Regression analyses examined associations between the 13 domains of needs (any need present: yes vs. no) and the three outcomes (patient activation, mental HRQoL, physical HRQoL). For the analysis of the PAM® scores, we combined levels 1–2 into *Lower patient activation* and levels 3–4 into *Higher patient activation* and used logistic regression with patient activation as the outcome (lower=0, higher=1). Linear regression analyses were conducted with Global Mental Health and Global Physical Health T-scores as outcomes. All models were adjusted for age, gender, education, European region, cancer type, and time since diagnosis.

In the first step, each domain of information and support needs was analyzed separately in relation to the outcomes, adjusted for confounders. In the second step, domains with associations at $p < 0.10$ were included in the multivariable models. In the final models, associations at $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant. Model assumptions, including multicollinearity, were checked prior to analysis.

2.3.4. Missing values

For the CCSS-NAQ, domain scores were calculated if $\geq 50\%$ of items within the domain were completed. For the PROMIS scales, all four

items had to be completed to calculate the Global Health scores [25]. For the PAM®, imputation for partially missing items was performed by the license holder; participants with all 13 items missing were excluded. Missing data on independent variables were handled by including a separate category in the regression analyses to maximize sample size and reduce potential bias from excluding participants with incomplete data.

3. Results

3.1. Participants

A total of 714 CAYACS accessed the questionnaire and completed the eligibility questions. Sixty-three were excluded for these analyses because they were younger than 18 years. Of the 651 eligible participants, 571 (88%) completed $\geq 50\%$ of items in at least one domain and

Table 1

Background characteristics of participants ($\geq 50\%$ of Items Completed in at Least One Domain of the CCSS-NAQ).

Variable	Category	N = 571	%	
Age at study	18–25 years	221	38.7	
	26–35 years	207	36.3	
	36–45 years	94	16.5	
	46–65 years	49	8.6	
Gender	Female	407	71.3	
	Male	160	28.0	
	Other / prefer not to answer	4	0.7	
European region	Northern Europe	119	20.8	
	Western Europe	162	28.4	
	Eastern Europe	71	12.4	
	Southern Europe	219	38.4	
Education level according to ISCED 2011	Primary/ lower secondary	40	7.0	
	Upper/post-secondary	135	23.6	
	Tertiary (Bachelor/Master/Doctorate)	230	40.3	
Age at diagnosis	Missing	166	29.1	
	< 1 years	16	2.8	
	1 – 4 years	66	11.6	
	5–9 years	64	11.2	
	10 – 14 years	110	19.3	
	15 – 19 years	107	18.7	
	20 – 24 years	51	8.9	
	Missing	157	27.5	
Time since diagnosis	< 5 years	54	9.5	
	5–10 years	86	15.1	
	> 10 years	267	46.8	
	Missing	164	28.7	
Primary cancer diagnosis	Leukemia	118	20.7	
	Lymphoma	121	21.2	
	Central nervous system tumor	32	5.6	
	Neuroblastoma	32	5.6	
	Retinoblastoma	6	1.1	
	Renal tumor	15	2.5	
	Malignant bone tumor	40	7.0	
	Soft tissue sarcoma	18	3.2	
	Germ cell tumor	13	2.3	
	Other	21	3.7	
	Missing	156	27.3	
	Follow-up care attendance	Yes	262	45.9
		No	137	24.0
		Missing	172	30.1
Late effects	No late effects	95	16.6	
	Non-neurocognitive late effects	104	18.2	
	Neurocognitive late effects	118	20.7	
	Unknown type of late effects	42	7.4	
	Missing	212	37.1	

****Note. CCSS-NAQ=Childhood Cancer Survivor Study-Needs Assessment Questionnaire. ISCED=International Standard Classification of Education. To minimize the risk of personal identification, response options were aggregated into broader categories already during data collection (e.g., age groups, time-since-diagnosis categories)

were included (Table 1). Most participants were in the age group 18–35 years (75.0%) and female (71.3%), with representation across Europe.

3.2. Prevalence of information and support needs

Fig. 1 presents the prevalence of information and support needs across the 13 domains. In all domains, except for spirituality, the majority of CAYACS reported a need (range: 62.0–90.3%). The proportion of CAYACS reporting high needs ranged from 4.3% to 23.3% across domains. The domains for which the largest proportion of CAYACS reported any needs were cancer-related health information (90.3%), psycho-emotional consequences (87.0%), and health system concerns (83.5%). In the spirituality domain, 27.3% of participants indicated any need, and only 4.3% reported a high need.

At the item level (Appendix C), most participants reported a high need on the items “Information about what I can do to reduce my chances of developing late effects” (39.2%), “Information about specific diseases that can result from cancer therapy” (36.3%), and “Information about which organ systems may have been affected by my cancer treatment” (33.7%).

3.3. Associations with socio-demographic and clinical characteristics

In multivariable models, several socio-demographic and clinical characteristics were associated with information and support needs (Table 2). Female survivors were more likely than males to report needs across several domains (psycho-emotional, survivor care and support, surveillance, relationships, and services; odds ratios (OR) ranging from 1.65 to 2.23).

Compared with Northern Europe, survivors from Western, Eastern, and Southern Europe were significantly more likely to report needs in several domains, most consistently in fiscal concerns (ORs 3.67–6.24) and nutrition (ORs 3.12–8.31). Survivors from Western and Eastern Europe were more likely to report needs in sexuality (ORs 2.06–4.19), and those from Eastern and Southern Europe in spirituality (ORs 3.39–5.18). The highest ORs were generally observed for Eastern Europe compared with Northern Europe. Additionally, survivors from Western Europe reported more psycho-emotional (OR=3.81, 95%CI 1.59–9.15)

and service needs (OR=2.04, 95%CI 1.18–3.53), whereas those from Eastern Europe were less likely to report cancer-related health information needs (OR=0.28, 95%CI 0.09–0.90). Details of regional prevalences are provided in Appendix D.

Survivors with any type of late effects had higher odds of reporting information and support needs than those without late effects (ORs 2.14–12.99; Table 2). Neurocognitive late effects were associated with all domains, except nutrition (ORs 2.14–12.99). The strongest associations were observed between experiencing neurocognitive late effects and reporting needs in general health (OR=12.99, 95%CI 4.68–36.06) and cancer-related health information (OR=8.97, 95%CI 1.93–41.65). Survivors diagnosed 5–10 and > 10 years ago (vs. <5 years) were less likely to report needs in nutrition (ORs 0.17–0.40) and spirituality (OR=0.35, 95%CI 0.15–0.77).

Age and follow-up care attendance were not associated with needs.

3.4. Patient activation and HRQoL

In analyses adjusted for potential confounders and conducted separately for each domain (Appendix E), information and support needs were consistently associated with lower patient activation and HRQoL. CAYACS reporting any need in a domain were less likely to have high patient activation (ORs 0.31–0.61) and had lower mental (B = -10.32 to -3.81) and physical (B = -9.26 to -4.31) HRQoL scores. The only exception was spirituality, which was not associated with patient activation.

When all domains that were significant in Step 1 were simultaneously included in the respective model, only a few associations remained significant (Table 3). General health needs were associated with lower global mental (B = -4.57, 95%CI -8.13 to -1.02) and physical (B = -5.15, 95%CI -8.92 to -1.37) health scores. Fiscal concerns were associated with lower physical health scores (B = -2.96, 95%CI -5.65 to -0.26). Relationship needs were associated with lower patient activation (OR=0.39, 95%CI 0.20–0.77) and lower global mental health scores (B = -3.41, 95%CI -6.19 to -0.64).

Fig. 1. Prevalence of Information and Support Needs Across 13 Domains.

Table 2
Multivariable Models with Sociodemographic and Clinical Predictors for Each Domain of Information and Support Needs (Any Need Present: Yes vs. No).

Domain information and support needs (part 1)	Psycho-emotional	Healthcare system	Cancer-related health information	General health	Survivor care and support	Surveillance	Coping
	OR (95% CI)	OR (95%CI)	OR (95%CI)	OR (95% CI)	OR (95% CI)	OR (95%CI)	OR (95%CI)
<i>Predictors</i>							
Age at study							
18–25 years	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
26–35 years	0.78 (0.42; 1.47)	1.06 (0.60; 1.88)	1.50 (0.70; 3.25)	1.19 (0.65; 2.18)	1.00 (0.53; 1.87)	1.26 (0.68; 2.32)	0.68 (0.36; 1.30)
36–45 years	0.98 (0.42; 2.27)	1.24 (0.57; 2.68)	2.34 (0.81; 6.75)	1.72 (0.78; 3.81)	1.27 (0.56; 2.87)	1.57 (0.71; 3.49)	1.00 (0.42; 2.35)
46 years and older	0.53 (0.20; 1.41)	1.46 (0.53; 4.00)	0.71 (0.24; 2.12)	1.91 (0.62; 5.85)	1.54 (0.50; 4.75)	1.34 (0.49; 3.71)	0.39 (0.15; 1.03)
Gender							
Male	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Female	1.76 (1.03; 3.02)*	1.62 (0.98; 2.68)	1.21 (0.62; 2.35)	1.40 (0.82; 2.38)	2.23 (1.31; 3.79)**	1.89 (1.12; 3.18)*	1.53 (0.89; 2.62)
Other	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
Region							
Northern Europe	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Western Europe	3.81 (1.59; 9.15)**	2.20 (0.95; 5.07)	0.94 (0.29; 3.10)	1.36 (0.63; 2.92)	1.59 (0.67; 3.76)	1.37 (0.63; 3.01)	1.86 (0.82; 4.18)
Eastern Europe	1.76 (0.71; 4.34)	0.72 (0.32; 1.63)	0.28 (0.09; 0.90)*	0.69 (0.30; 1.61)	1.11 (0.44; 2.81)	1.12 (0.45; 2.82)	1.09 (0.43; 2.73)
Southern Europe	1.31 (0.68; 2.54)	0.66 (0.34; 1.27)	0.42 (0.15; 1.18)	1.28 (0.63; 2.60)	0.72 (0.35; 1.46)	0.83 (0.42; 1.64)	0.99 (0.50; 1.96)
Time since diagnosis							
< 5 years	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
5–10 years	0.60 (0.17; 2.10)	1.21 (0.42; 3.54)	0.32 (0.03; 2.97)	1.31 (0.41; 4.21)	0.34 (0.09; 1.29)	0.77 (0.26; 2.26)	0.74 (0.26; 2.11)
> 10 years	0.57 (0.18; 1.81)	0.81 (0.31; 2.06)	0.13 (0.02; 1.09)	0.44 (0.16; 1.17)	0.29 (0.08; 1.05)	0.42 (0.16; 1.11)	0.68 (0.26; 1.74)
Missing	0.68 (0.13; 3.73)	0.43 (0.11; 1.78)	0.11 (0.01; 1.37)	0.50 (0.11; 2.21)	0.21 (0.04; 1.11)	0.52 (0.13; 2.19)	0.83 (0.18; 3.82)
Follow-up care attendance							
No	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Yes	0.91 (0.48; 1.73)	1.18 (0.65; 2.15)	1.14 (0.51; 2.55)	0.98 (0.53; 1.80)	1.40 (0.76; 2.56)	0.98 (0.55; 1.75)	1.33 (0.76; 2.34)
Missing	0.96 (0.24; 3.89)	1.15 (0.34; 3.85)	0.57 (0.11; 2.83)	0.88 (0.25; 3.08)	0.81 (0.24; 2.77)	0.63 (0.19; 2.06)	1.48 (0.41; 5.36)
Late effects							
No late effects	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Non-neurocognitive late effects	2.06 (0.95; 4.48)	1.35 (0.64; 2.85)	1.25 (0.53; 2.99)	3.50 (1.68; 7.30)**	1.05 (0.50; 2.18)	1.24 (0.62; 2.47)	2.78 (1.37; 5.66)**
Neurocognitive late effects	4.77 (1.86; 12.25)***	2.40 (1.06; 5.43)*	8.97 (1.93; 41.65)**	12.99 (4.68; 36.06)***	2.51 (1.07; 5.90)*	2.33 (1.10; 4.95)*	4.73 (2.14; 10.43)***
Unknown type of late effects	5.52 (1.18; 25.85)*	1.80 (0.55; 5.92)	7.13 (0.84; 60.22)	6.86 (1.88; 25.00)**	8.40 (1.05; 67.03)*	12.22 (1.55; 96.11)*	6.66 (1.81; 24.47)**
Missing	1.74 (0.73; 4.12)	1.79 (0.76; 4.22)	2.94 (0.95; 9.12)	2.83 (1.27; 6.30)*	1.44 (0.62; 3.34)	1.52 (0.69; 3.38)	1.82 (0.84; 3.94)
Domain information and support needs (part 2)							
	Fiscal OR (95% CI)	Relationships OR (95%CI)	Sexuality OR (95%CI)	Services OR (95%CI)	Nutrition OR (95% CI)	Spirituality OR (95%CI)	
<i>Predictors</i>							
Age at study							
18–25 years	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Domain information and support needs (part 1)	Psycho-emotional	Healthcare system	Cancer-related health information	General health	Survivor care and support	Surveillance	Coping
	OR (95% CI)	OR (95%CI)	OR (95%CI)	OR (95% CI)	OR (95% CI)	OR (95%CI)	OR (95%CI)
26–35 years	1.11 (0.61; 2.01)	1.02 (0.57; 1.82)	0.58 (0.34; 0.98) *	1.18 (0.60; 2.30)	1.08 (0.63; 1.87)	0.65 (0.37; 1.15)	
36–45 years	0.90 (0.43; 1.86)	0.85 (0.41; 1.74)	0.56 (0.29; 1.11)	1.04 (0.45; 2.42)	0.94 (0.47; 1.88)	0.85 (0.40; 1.77)	
46 years and older	1.42 (0.54; 3.69)	0.81 (0.33; 2.01)	0.49 (0.21; 1.12)	0.72 (0.26; 1.98)	1.08 (0.44; 2.67)	0.35 (0.12; 0.98)*	
Gender							
Female vs. Male	1.54 (0.92; 2.56)	1.65 (1.01; 2.70)*	1.49 (0.93; 2.38)	2.04 (1.18; 3.53)*	1.08 (0.66; 1.76)	1.34 (0.78; 2.28)	
Other vs. Male	NE	NE	NE	NE	1.53 (0.12; 19.38)	NE	
Region							
Northern Europe	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	
Western Europe	3.67 (1.90; 7.10)***	1.78 (0.91; 3.49)	2.06 (1.13; 3.75) *	2.40 (1.04; 5.55)*	3.12 (1.69; 5.77)***	1.60 (0.77; 3.33)	
Eastern Europe	6.24 (2.39; 16.28)***	1.02 (0.45; 2.33)	4.19 (1.75; 10.03)**	1.21 (0.47; 3.10)	8.31 (3.20; 21.57)***	5.18 (2.19; 12.25)***	
Southern Europe	3.83 (2.06; 7.11)***	1.62 (0.86; 3.02)	1.74 (0.99; 3.06)	1.31 (0.65; 2.66)	3.38 (1.89; 6.06)***	3.39 (1.71; 6.72)***	
Time since diagnosis							
< 5 years	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	
5–10 years	0.75 (0.27; 2.03)	0.98 (0.39; 2.44)	1.27 (0.57; 2.81)	0.39 (0.13; 1.18)	0.30 (0.13; 0.72)**	0.35 (0.15; 0.77)**	
> 10 years	0.42 (0.17; 1.04)	0.55 (0.25; 1.24)	0.82 (0.41; 1.65)	0.43 (0.15; 1.24)	0.40 (0.18; 0.90)*	0.50 (0.25; 1.03)	
Missing	0.39 (0.09; 1.68)	0.69 (0.18; 2.56)	0.73 (0.20; 2.71)	0.34 (0.07; 1.67)	0.17 (0.04; 0.67)*	0.66 (0.15; 2.83)	
Follow-up care attendance							
No	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	
Yes	1.22 (0.73; 2.04)	0.99 (0.60; 1.65)	1.24 (0.78; 1.98)	1.17 (0.66; 2.09)	1.28 (0.79; 2.06)	0.73 (0.43; 1.22)	
Missing	1.32 (0.40; 4.32)	0.70 (0.24; 2.05)	1.22 (0.43; 3.51)	0.87 (0.26; 2.95)	1.45 (0.47; 4.46)	0.76 (0.25; 2.34)	
Neurocognitive late effects							
No late effects	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	
Non-neurocognitive late effects	1.54 (0.80; 2.96)	3.00 (1.56; 5.76)**	2.40 (1.29; 4.50)**	1.99 (0.96; 4.12)	1.42 (0.76; 2.67)	2.22 (1.08; 4.53)*	
Neurocognitive late effects	5.66 (2.62; 12.25)***	3.84 (1.97; 7.48)***	2.14 (1.16; 3.95)*	2.77 (1.29; 5.94)**	1.78 (0.95; 3.33)	2.32 (1.16; 4.61)*	
Unknown type of late effects	2.02 (0.82; 4.99)	4.83 (1.77; 13.17)**	2.58 (1.12; 5.95)*	4.49 (1.21; 16.67)*	3.63 (1.41; 9.30)**	3.11 (1.26; 7.71)*	
Missing	2.01 (0.94; 4.33)	2.46 (1.19; 5.11)*	1.64 (0.81; 3.29)	2.07 (0.91; 4.72)	1.89 (0.91; 3.92)	1.30 (0.58; 2.92)	

***Note. Ref.=Reference category, NE=Non estimable: too few participants in this category (n = 4) with insufficient outcome variation.

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001. Significant results are presented in bold

4. Discussion

4.1. Main findings

Information and support needs were highly prevalent among

CAYACS across Europe, with particularly high needs in cancer-related health information, psycho-emotional consequences, and health system concerns. Females, those residing in Eastern Europe, and survivors with neurocognitive late effects were particularly likely to report needs. Needs were associated with lower patient activation and poorer HRQoL.

Table 3
Multivariable Models Examining the Associations of Information and Support Needs (Any vs. No Need) with Patient Activation (PAM®) and Mental and Physical Global Health (PROMIS).

Outcomes	PAM® (low vs. high) OR (95%CI)	PROMIS global mental T-score B (95%CI)	PROMIS global physical T-score B (95% CI)
Predictors			
Information needs (any vs. no need)			
Psycho-emotional	1.54 (0.62; 3.84)	-2.32 (-6.09; 1.44)	-0.86 (-4.85; 3.13)
Health system concerns	0.73 (0.30; 1.78)	-1.65 (-5.04; 1.75)	-1.87 (-5.46; 1.73)
Cancer-related health information	0.56 (0.19; 1.63)	2.45 (-1.64; 6.55)	2.29 (-2.06; 6.63)
General health	1.06 (0.44; 2.57)	-4.57 (-8.13; -1.02)*	-5.15 (-8.92; -1.37)**
Survivor care & support	1.00 (0.37; 2.70)	2.06 (-1.86; 5.98)	-0.29 (-4.46; 3.88)
Surveillance	0.84 (0.37; 1.90)	-1.34 (-4.63; 1.94)	1.63 (-1.92; 5.18)
Coping	0.97 (0.42; 2.22)	-2.94 (-6.49; 0.61)	-1.23 (-5.00; 2.53)
Fiscal concerns	0.83 (0.44; 1.59)	-0.40 (-2.94; 2.14)	-2.96 (-5.65; -0.26)*
Relationships	0.39 (0.20; 0.77)**	-3.41 (-6.19; -0.64)*	-1.06 (-4.00; 1.88)
Sexuality	1.10 (0.63; 1.93)	-1.53 (-3.69; 0.64)	-0.93 (-3.23; 1.37)
Services	1.09 (0.50; 2.40)	-0.53 (-3.65; 2.58)	-1.24 (-4.54; 2.07)
Nutrition	0.58 (0.32; 1.03)	-0.97 (-3.29; 1.34)	-0.24 (-2.73; 2.24)
Spirituality*	-	-0.31 (-2.59; 1.96)	-1.75 (-4.18; 0.68)

**** Notes.

CNS=Central Nervous System. Ref.=Reference category. NE=Non estimable: too few participants in this category (n = 4) with insufficient outcome variation. Spirituality was not included in the PAM model, as it was not statistically significant in the pre-selection (see **Appendix E**).

The analysis was adjusted for age at study, gender, region, education, time since diagnosis, and diagnosis.

* p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001. Significant results are presented in **bold**.

4.2. Prevalence of needs

The prevalence of information and support needs in our study was high: across 12 of the 13 domains (all except spirituality), between 62% and 90% of participants reported at least one need. This is consistent with the results of a recent systematic review, which also reported unmet needs among CAYACS across multiple life domains, with prevalence rates up to 91% [1]. These findings underscore the long-term nature of information and supportive care needs in this population, which may reflect survivorship challenges—such as late effects—that can persist or emerge throughout the life course [5,7].

The high prevalence of cancer-related health information and psycho-emotional needs (84–90%) suggests that many CAYACS remain concerned about their health, potential late effects, and psychological well-being. In our study, the most frequently reported needs related to late effects, including information on how to reduce risks, possible treatment-related diseases, and affected organ systems. These findings, consistent with earlier research [1], highlight that late effects are a major concern in survivorship [5,7]. Such health challenges, together with the cancer experience itself, may lead to anxiety, depression, and distress [28,29]. Many CAYACS continue to report cancer-related worries [30], which may contribute to needs across physical and psychosocial domains. Information needs may also arise when information was initially provided to parents or at an age when survivors were too young to fully understand or remember it [1]. Lower spiritual needs may

reflect secularization across European countries [31].

4.3. Socio-demographic and clinical associated factors

Several socio-demographic and clinical characteristics were associated with reporting information and support needs. Female survivors were more likely than males to report needs across multiple domains. This is consistent with prior evidence [1], and may reflect gender differences in health information behaviors, with women generally being more interested in and engaging more actively in seeking health-related information than men [32].

A novel finding was the clear regional variation observed: CAYACS residing in Western, Southern, and particularly Eastern Europe were significantly more likely to report needs in domains such as fiscal concerns, services, nutrition, or spirituality compared with those in Northern Europe. These patterns may reflect variations in health care systems, availability of survivorship care, and cultural norms surrounding help-seeking [9]. Interestingly, CAYACS from Eastern European countries, where survivorship care is often less systematically available (European map - PanCare), were less likely to report needs regarding cancer-related health information than those from Northern Europe. Limited follow-up care may reduce survivors' awareness of potential late effects or prevent them from linking existing health concerns to their previous cancer treatment, resulting in fewer questions being raised in the context of survivorship. This does not mean that follow-up care is less important in these regions; on the contrary, it highlights the need to strengthen survivorship services so that late effects can be adequately recognized and addressed.

Although previous studies have identified an association between the presence of late effects and information needs [10,13]—a finding confirmed by the present study—the specific impact of neurocognitive late effects had not been examined. Our results showed that neurocognitive late effects were consistently associated with the presence of information and support needs, particularly in the cancer-related health information and general health domains. Survivors with neurocognitive difficulties may face greater challenges in managing follow-up care, processing health-related information, and navigating daily life, which can contribute to increased needs. These findings highlight the importance of paying particular attention to this subgroup and ensuring that information and support are tailored to their cognitive abilities.

Survivors with a longer time since diagnosis were less likely to report needs in the domains of nutrition and spirituality. This may suggest that CAYACS adapt and accumulate information over time, making some needs less prominent. However, a previous study [11] reported greater information needs regarding specific problems such as pain and fatigue with increasing time since diagnosis. It is plausible that needs related to specific late effects increase over time, as late effects may emerge and accumulate many years after diagnosis [7].

Interestingly, neither age at study nor follow-up care attendance were associated with information and support needs. Survivors from different age groups may experience distinct types of needs [33], without one group reporting overall higher levels than others. Attending long-term follow-up does not necessarily mean that information about late effects is provided [34]. Even when such information is given, it can be experienced as a double-edged sword; it can equip survivors with knowledge and skills, but at the same time heighten awareness and worries, thereby increasing survivors' need for additional information and care [15]. Therefore, information on late effects should be delivered in a stepwise and personalized manner, with attention to the emotional responses it may evoke and the additional questions or support needs that may arise.

4.4. Associations with patient activation and HRQoL

Previous studies found that unmet information needs were associated with poorer HRQoL [35,36]. Our study showed that CAYACS

reporting needs additionally demonstrated lower patient activation. Patient activation is an important predictor of health service use as well as better health outcomes and care experiences [17]. This is particularly relevant for CAYACS, who are at risk of late effects and are advised to attend regular follow-up care. Ensuring that CAYACS are provided with adequate information and support may improve their well-being and strengthen their ability to manage their health and care effectively.

Supporting survivors with information on general health, fiscal concerns and relationship questions—alongside addressing highly prevalent needs such as cancer-related health information and psycho-emotional needs—may be particularly useful.

4.5. Strengths and limitations

This study has several strengths, including its large and diverse sample of participants from multiple European countries, the use of a comprehensive and validated measure of information and support needs, and its broad scope including predictors of both information and support needs and outcomes (patient activation and HRQoL).

Nevertheless, this study has several limitations. First, because recruitment occurred through open channels, it was not possible to determine how many CAYACS were reached, preventing the calculation of a response rate or comparison of participants with non-participants. The high proportion of female participants (71%) and the low proportion of survivors with lower education (7%), or a CNS tumor (5%) suggest that males, survivors with lower educational levels and survivors of CNS tumors may be underrepresented. The relatively low representation of CNS tumor survivors in our study may have resulted in an underrepresentation of needs in certain domains, as survivors of CNS tumors more frequently experience (neurocognitive) late effects and have been reported to have greater information needs [1,37]. In addition, self-selection bias may have influenced participation. For example, individuals with greater information needs may have been more motivated to participate because the study addressed their concerns. Conversely, survivors with the highest needs may represent a more vulnerable group and may therefore have been less likely to participate. Thus, the direction of potential bias remains unclear. Second, missing data were present across several background variables. To maximize retention of participants in the analyses, missing values were included in the analyses using a separate category. Nevertheless, the potential influence of missing data on the findings cannot be ruled out. Third, the cross-sectional design of this study hinders causal inferences. While lower HRQoL may result from unmet information needs, it is also possible that survivors with lower HRQoL are more likely to report such needs. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to detect how needs evolve over time, although the observed negative association between time since diagnosis and certain needs suggests that some needs may decrease over time. Finally, no correction for multiple testing was applied due to the exploratory nature of the study. Therefore, chance findings cannot be ruled out and should be considered when interpreting the results. Despite these limitations, the study provides important insights into the information and support needs of CAYACS across Europe.

4.6. Implications for practice and future research

Our findings have several implications for survivorship care. First, the high prevalence of needs underscores the importance of routinely assessing and addressing information and support needs among CAYACS, even many years after treatment. Clinicians may simply ask CAYACS about current psychosocial and health-related needs or use a validated measure such as the CCSS-NAQ for the assessment of these needs [21]. Future research should focus on developing a short version of the CCSS-NAQ for clinical use, covering domains that are most relevant both in terms of prevalence (cancer-related health information, psycho-emotional consequences, and health system concerns, including information about after-cancer care), and in terms of impact on patient

activation and HRQoL (general health, fiscal and relationship needs).

Second, given the high prevalence of needs among CAYACS, survivorship care programs should integrate accessible information on long-term health risks and other life domains into standard follow-up care. An information session around age 25 years may be particularly valuable, as CAYACS by then feel ready to receive such information and take responsibility for their health [38]. Additionally, supporting adolescents and young adults during the transition from pediatric to adult care is essential [39].

When communicating about late effects, it is important to recognize that such information may also trigger worries [38]. A stepwise approach is therefore advisable, in which clinicians check whether survivors want more detail before proceeding [38]. Tailoring information to individual needs and risks can further improve the accuracy of survivors' risk perceptions [40]. Because information about late effects can be stressful, information should be delivered in a sensitive, empathetic, and patient-centered manner [41]. Moreover, clear points of contact should be available so that CAYACS know whom to approach if concerns arise.

Written information is also highly valued [38], and has been associated with lower information needs [10]. A survivorship passport containing essential information on diagnosis, treatment, and risk for late effects has been proposed as a practical tool that both meets survivors' need for accessible written information and facilitates communication with other healthcare providers [42].

Third, the strong regional variation in information and support needs highlights inequity in survivorship care across Europe and underscores the need for harmonized guidelines and equitable access to resources. The e-QuoL project is developing e-health tools, such as apps and informational website content, and promotes the implementation of survivorship passports across Europe, to help address these needs. Over time, such efforts may contribute to reducing regional inequalities. These initiatives align with the goals of the Next Level EU Cancer Survivorship and Quality-of-Life Policy, which emphasizes equitable survivorship care, digital support tools, survivorship care plans, and improved quality of life for cancer survivors across Europe [43].

4.7. Conclusion

Information and support needs remain highly prevalent among European CAYACS, even many years after diagnosis. Females, survivors residing in Eastern European regions, and those with neurocognitive late effects appear to be particularly likely to report such needs. It is important to address these needs, as they are consistently associated with lower patient activation and poorer HRQoL. Therefore, routine needs assessment from diagnosis through follow-up care is essential. Tailored strategies—such as accessible written information, digital tools, and survivorship passports—could be integrated into targeted, equitable, and long-term survivorship care to optimize the well-being and quality of life of this growing population.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Anne Maas: Conceptualization, Data collection, Analysis, Writing – original draft. **Valeriia Balaeva:** Conceptualization, Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Maëlle de Ville de Goyet:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Jelica Predojevic:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Jelena Roganovic:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Charlotte Demoor-Goldschmidt:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Amandine Bertrand:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Päivi Lähteenmäki:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Mira Pomrén:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Eugenie Werbenko:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Beate Timmermann:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Magdalena Balcerek:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Miklós Garami:** Data collection, Writing –

review & editing. **Zsuzsanna Jakab:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Monica Muraca:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Sara Oberti:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Hanne C. Lie:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Kristen E.T. Thornton:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Lorna Zadavec Zaletel:** Data collection, Writing – review & editing. **Katharina Roser:** Conceptualization, Data collection, Analysis, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Anica Ilic:** Conceptualization, Data collection, Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Gisela Michel:** Conceptualization, Data collection, Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Supervision.

Consent to participate

All participants provided written informed consent.

Consent for publication

This study does not include any individual, identifiable participant data requiring consent for publication.

Funding

The project e-QuoL, number 101136549, is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe, granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all survivors who participated in this study. We would also like to thank all partners of the e-QuoL consortium (<https://equolproject.eu/consortium/>) for their support in recruiting participants and translating the questionnaires into local languages. We thank research assistant Aline Wechsler for her contributions to data collection and data curation.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ejcped.2026.100528](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcped.2026.100528).

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

- [1] A. Maas, E. Bertolini, K. Ostheim, H.C. Lie, C. Demoor-Goldschmidt, M. Garami, G. Michel, A. Ilic, Information needs of adult childhood, adolescent, and young adult cancer survivors (CAYACS): a systematic review, *Patient Educ. Couns.* 146 (2026) 109506 (May).
- [2] C.L. Cox, L. Zhu, R.P. Ojha, C. Li, D.K. Srivastava, B.B. Riley, M.M. Hudson, L. Robison, The unmet emotional, care/support, and informational needs of adult survivors of pediatric malignancies, *J. Cancer Surviv.* 10 (4) (2016) 743–758.
- [3] L.M.E. Van Erp, H. Maurice-Stam, L.C.M. Kremer, W.J.E. Tissing, H.J.H. Van Der Pal, L. Beek, A.C.H. De Vries, M.M. Van Den Heuvel-Eibrink, Ba.B. Versluys, M. Van Der Heiden-Van Der Loo, M. Van Gorp, G.A. Huizinga, M.A. Grootenhuys, Support needs of Dutch young adult childhood cancer survivors, *Support. Care Cancer* 30 (4) (2022) 3291–3302.
- [4] M.J. Hendriks, E. Harju, G. Michel, The unmet needs of childhood cancer survivors in long-term follow-up care: a qualitative study, *Psychooncology* 30 (4) (2021) 485–492.
- [5] M.M. Geenen, M.C. Cardous-Ubbink, L.C. Kremer, C. Van Den Bos, H.J. Van Der Pal, R.C. Heinen, M.W. Jaspers, C.C. Koning, F. Oldenburger, N.E. Langeveld, A. A. Hart, P.J. Bakker, H.N. Caron, F.E. Van Leeuwen, Medical assessment of adverse health outcomes in long-term survivors of childhood cancer, *JAMA* 297 (24) (2007) 2705–2715.
- [6] G. Michel, T.M. Brinkman, C.E. Wakefield, M. Grootenhuys, Psychological outcomes, health-related quality of life, and neurocognitive functioning in survivors of childhood cancer and their parents, *Pediatr. Clin. North. Am.* 67 (6) (2020) 1103–1134.
- [7] N. Streefkerk, J.C. Teepen, Ea.M. Feijen, K. Jozwiak, H.J.H. Van Der Pal, C. M. Ronckers, A.C.H. De Vries, M. Van Der Heiden-Van Der Loo, N. Hollema, M. Van Den Berg, J. Loonen, M.A. Grootenhuys, D. Bresters, A.B. Versluys, E. Van Dulmen-Den Broeder, M.M. Van Den Heuvel-Eibrink, F.E. Van Leeuwen, S. Neggers, H. M. Van Santen, M. Hawkins, M. Hauptmann, D. Yoneoka, J.C. Korevaar, W.J. E. Tissing, L.C.M. Kremer, D.L.S. Group, The cumulative burden of self-reported, clinically relevant outcomes in long-term childhood cancer survivors and implications for survivorship care: a DCCSS LATER study, *Cancer* 130 (8) (2024) 1349–1358.
- [8] G. Michel, R.L. Mulder, H.J.H. Van Der Pal, R. Skinner, E. Bardi, M.C. Brown, J. Vetsch, E. Frey, R. Windsor, L.C.M. Kremer, G. Levitt, Evidence-based recommendations for the organization of long-term follow-up care for childhood and adolescent cancer survivors: a report from the PanCareSurFup Guidelines Working Group, *J. Cancer Surviv.* 13 (5) (2019) 759–772.
- [9] G. Vassal, M. Schrappe, K. Pritchard-Jones, F. Arnold, L. Basset, A. Biondi, G. Bode, A. Eggert, L. Hjorth, L. Kamerić, N. Kamerić, S. Karner, P. Kearns, A. Kienesberger, J. Kowalczyk, P. Lack, G. Perilongo, R. Sullivan, A. Tsiros, S. Essiaf, R. Ladenstein, The SIOPE strategic plan: a European cancer plan for children and adolescents, *J. Cancer Policy* 8 (2016) 17–32.
- [10] E. Hövén, B. Lannering, G. Gustafsson, K.K. Boman, Information needs of survivors and families after childhood CNS tumor treatment: a population-based study, *Acta Oncol.* 57 (5) (2018) 649–657.
- [11] L. Kelada, C.E. Wakefield, L.C. Heathcote, T. Jaaniste, C. Signorelli, J.E. Fardell, M. Donoghoe, M.C. Mccarthy, M. Gabriel, R.J. Cohn, A.S.S. Group, Perceived cancer-related pain and fatigue, information needs, and fear of cancer recurrence among adult survivors of childhood cancer, *Patient Educ. Couns.* 102 (12) (2019) 2270–2278.
- [12] J. Vetsch, C.E. Wakefield, K.M. Tucker, M. Mccarthy, C. Signorelli, T. Walwyn, F. Alvaro, R.J. Cohn, A.S.S. Group, Genetics-related service and information needs of childhood cancer survivors and parents: a mixed-methods study, *Eur. J. Hum. Genet.* 28 (1) (2020) 6–16.
- [13] W. Mccllellan, J.R. Klemp, H. Krebill, R. Ryan, E.L. Nelson, J. Panicker, M. Sharma, K. Stegenga, Understanding the functional late effects and informational needs of adult survivors of childhood cancer, *Oncol. Nurs. Forum* 40 (3) (2013) 254–262.
- [14] P.A. Larsen, A. Amidi, N. Ghith, J.F. Winther, C. Pedersen, Quality of life of adolescent and adult survivors of childhood cancer in Europe-A systematic review, *Int. J. Cancer* 153 (7) (2023) 1356–1375.
- [15] J. Vetsch, J.E. Fardell, C.E. Wakefield, C. Signorelli, G. Michel, J.K. Mcloone, T. Walwyn, H. Tapp, J. Truscott, R.J. Cohn, A.S.S. Group, "Forewarned and forearmed": long-term childhood cancer survivors' and parents' information needs and implications for survivorship models of care, *Patient Educ. Couns.* 100 (2) (2017) 355–363.
- [16] R. Kearns, B. Harris-Roxas, J. Mcdonald, H.J. Song, S. Dennis, M. Harris, Implementing the Patient Activation Measure (PAM) in clinical settings for patients with chronic conditions: a scoping review, *Integr. Healthc. J.* 2 (1) (2020) e000032.
- [17] J.H. Hibbard, J. Greene, What the evidence shows about patient activation: better health outcomes and care experiences; fewer data on costs, *Health Aff. (Millwood)* 32 (2) (2013) 207–214.
- [18] J. Hibberd, H. Gilbert, Supporting people to manage their health: an introduction to patient activation, *King's. Fund.* (2014).
- [19] R. Requier, C. Gimenez, M. Muraca, P.M. Lähteenmäki, A.S. Gresle, L.T. Henriksen, B. Marion, G. Benoit, K.E.T. Thornton, C. Demoor-Goldschmidt, The e-QuoL project: enhancing long-term follow-up care for childhood cancer survivors through digital innovation, results of an exploratory questionnaire, *J. Cancer Surviv.* (2025).
- [20] E. Steliarova-Foucher, C. Stiller, B. Lacour, P. Kaatsch, International classification of childhood, *Cancer Third Ed. Cancer* 103 (7) (2005) 1457–1467.
- [21] C.L. Cox, D.A. Sherrill-Mittleman, B.B. Riley, M.M. Hudson, L.J. Williams, W. M. Leisenring, M.G. Zacher, L.L. Robison, Development of a comprehensive health-related needs assessment for adult survivors of childhood cancer, *J. Cancer Surviv.* 7 (1) (2013) 1–19.
- [22] J.H. Hibbard, J. Stockard, E.R. Mahoney, M. Tusler, Development of the Patient Activation Measure (PAM): conceptualizing and measuring activation in patients and consumers, *Health Serv. Res.* 39 (4 Pt 1) (2004) 1005–1026.
- [23] Insignia Health. Patient Activation Measure® (PAM®). 2025 [cited 2025]; Available from: (<https://www.insigniahealth.com/pam/>).
- [24] I. Roessel, D. Froehlich, S. Joos, J. Valentini, H. Mauch, P. Martus, The Patient Activation Measure-13 (PAM-13) in an oncology patient population: psychometric properties and dimensionality evaluation, *Health Qual. Life Outcomes* 22 (1) (2024) 39.

- [25] R.D. Hays, J.B. Bjorner, D.A. Revicki, K.L. Spritzer, D. Cella, Development of physical and mental health summary scores from the patient-reported outcomes measurement information system (PROMIS) global items, *Qual. Life Res.* 18 (7) (2009) 873–880.
- [26] Unesco, *International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED)*, 2011.
- [27] **United Nations geoscheme for Europe. 2023; Available from:** (<https://unstats.un.org/unsd/methodology/m49/>).
- [28] A. Maas, H. Maurice-Stam, L. Feijen, J.C. Teepen, A.M. Van Der Aa-Van Delden, N. Streefkerk, E. Van Dulmen-Den Broeder, W.J.E. Tissing, J.J. Loonen, H.J.H. Van Der Pal, A.C.H. De Vries, M.M. Van Den Heuvel-Eibrink, C. Ronckers, S. Neggers, D. Bresters, M. Louwerens, Ba.B. Versluys, M. Van Der Heiden-Van Der Loo, L.C. M. Kremer, M. Grootenhuis, L.S.G. Dutch, The impact of clinically relevant health conditions on psychosocial outcomes in survivors of childhood cancer: results of the DCCSS-LATER study, *J. Cancer Surviv.* (2024).
- [29] P.F. Raguindin, C.S. Rueegg, S. Kälin, E. Bergstraesser, N.X. Von Der Weid, E. M. Tinner, C.E. Kuehni, G. Michel, Longitudinal changes of psychological distress among childhood cancer survivors: The Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study, *Pediatr. Blood Cancer* 71 (8) (2024) e31095.
- [30] A. Maas, A. Westerweel, H. Maurice-Stam, L.C.M. Kremer, A.M. Van Der Aa-Van Delden, D. Zwerus, E.C. Van Dalen, M.A. Grootenhuis, The Prevalence and Associated Factors of Cancer-Related Worries in Adult Survivors of Childhood Cancer: A Systematic Review, *Psychooncology* 34 (2) (2025) e70101.
- [31] J. Stolz, N.D. De Graaf, C. Hackett, J.-P. Antonietti, The three stages of religious decline around the world, *Nat. Commun.* 16 (1) (2025) 7202.
- [32] S. Ek, Gender differences in health information behaviour: a Finnish population-based survey, *Health Promot. Int.* 30 (3) (2015) 736–745.
- [33] A.E. Darlington, C.E. Wakefield, L.M.E. Van Erp, W.T.A. Van Der Graaf, R.J. Cohn, M.A. Grootenhuis, Psychosocial consequences of surviving cancer diagnosed and treated in childhood versus in adolescence/young adulthood: a call for clearer delineation between groups, *Cancer* 128 (14) (2022) 2690–2694.
- [34] A.V. Mellblom, L. Korsvold, A. Finset, J. Loge, E. Ruud, H.C. Lie, Providing information about late effects during routine follow-up consultations between pediatric oncologists and adolescent survivors: a video-based, observational study, *J. Adolesc. Young-Adult Oncol.* 4 (4) (2015) 200–208.
- [35] S. Christen, E. Weishaupt, J. Vetsch, C.S. Rueegg, L. Mader, S. Dehler, G. Michel, Perceived information provision and information needs in adolescent and young adult cancer survivors, *Eur J Cancer Care (Engl)* 28 (1) (2019) e12892.
- [36] M.E. Gianinazzi, S. Essig, C.S. Rueegg, N.X. Von Der Weid, P. Brazzola, C. E. Kuehni, G. Michel, Swiss Paediatric Oncology, G., Information provision and information needs in adult survivors of childhood cancer, *Pediatr. Blood Cancer* 61 (2) (2014) 312–318.
- [37] G.T. Armstrong, Q. Liu, Y. Yasui, S. Huang, K.K. Ness, W. Leisenring, M.M. Hudson, S.S. Donaldson, A.A. King, M. Stovall, K.R. Krull, L.L. Robison, R.J. Packer, Long-term outcomes among adult survivors of childhood central nervous system malignancies in the Childhood Cancer Survivor Study, *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.* 101 (13) (2009) 946–958.
- [38] H.C. Lie, J.H. Loge, S.D. Fosså, H.M. Hamre, S.L. Hess, A.V. Mellblom, E. Ruud, A. Finset, Providing information about late effects after childhood cancer: lymphoma survivors' preferences for what, how and when, *Patient Educ. Couns.* 98 (5) (2015) 604–611.
- [39] J. Wams, E.C. Van Dalen, J.G. Den Hartogh, M. Otth, T. Costa, J.W. Gorter, A. M. Van Der Aa-Van Delden, A. Panasiuk, B. Wörmann, C. Berger, E. Bardi, E. H. Larsen, E. Potter, E.L. Soria, G. Levitt, G. Michel, H.J.H. Van Der Pal, J. Roganovic, J. De Bont, L. Wauters, L. Pelanconi, L.Z. Zaletel, M. Balcersek, M. Muraca, M.C. Brown, O.A. Asogwa, O. De Sousa, R. Koopman, S. Mehta, V. Papadakis, L.C.M. Kremer, R. Skinner, K. Scheinemann, R.L. Mulder, A. Kienesberger, K. Rizvi, S. Essiaf, H.J. Van Der Pal, L.C.M. Kremer, N. Ciakienė, B. Nafria Escalera, U. Leiss, K.B. O'Brien, Health-care transitions for young people living beyond childhood and adolescent cancer: recommendations from the EU-CAYAS-NET consortium, *Lancet Oncol.* 26 (10) (2025) e525–e535.
- [40] A. Albada, M.G. Ausems, J.M. Bensing, S. Van Dulmen, Tailored information about cancer risk and screening: a systematic review, *Patient Educ. Couns.* 77 (2) (2009) 155–171.
- [41] B. Zebrack, M.A. Chesler, S. Kaplan, To foster healing among adolescents and young adults with cancer: what helps? What hurts? *Support. Care Cancer* 18 (1) (2010) 131–135.
- [42] R. Haupt, S. Essiaf, C. Dellacasa, C.M. Ronckers, S. Caruso, E. Sugden, L. Zadravec Zaletel, M. Muraca, V. Morsellino, A. Kienesberger, A. Blondeel, D. Saraceno, M. Ortali, L.C.M. Kremer, R. Skinner, J. Roganovic, F. Bagnasco, G.A. Levitt, M. De Rosa, M. Schrappe, L. Hjorth, R. Ladenstein, E.W.G. Pancaresurfup, Expo-R-Net Working, G. The 'Survivorship Passport' for childhood cancer survivors. *Eur. J. Cancer* 102 (2018) 69–81.
- [43] E.C. Organisation, Next Level EU Cancer Survivorship and Quality-of-Life Policy: A Reflection on Progress and Gaps: Are We Doing Enough? European Cancer Organisation, Brussels, 2024.

Appendices

Information and Support Needs of Childhood, Adolescent, and Young Adult Cancer Survivors (CAYACS) Across Europe and Associations with Patient Activation and Health-Related Quality of Life: *Results from the e-QuoL Project*

Anne Maas, Valeriia Balaeva, Maëlle de Ville de Goyet, Jelica Predojevic, Jelena Roganovic, Charlotte Demoor-Goldschmidt, Amandine Bertrand, Päivi Lähteenmäki, Mira Pomrén, Eugenie Werbenko, Beate Timmermann, Magdalena Balcerek, Miklós Garami, Zsuzsanna Jakab, Monica Muraca, Sara Oberti, Hanne C. Lie, Kristen E.T. Thornton, Lorna Zadavec Zaletel, Katharina Roser, Anica Ilic, Gisela Michel

Appendix A Detailed Study Procedure

Recruitment by country

The recruitment process was coordinated by 25 e-QuoL project partners from 15 countries, including hospitals, universities, and survivor organizations. Recruitment channels primarily included social media platforms, such as Instagram and Facebook (n=19 partners), personal contacts during follow-up care and collaborations with patient organizations (both n=17), mailing lists or newsletters (n=13), and, less frequently, distribution of leaflets or blog posts with links to the survey (n=7). No cancer registries were used for recruitment. Given the nature of the recruitment strategies, the number of individuals reached was unknown, and therefore the response rate could not be calculated. No personally identifiable information (e.g., names, contact details, IP addresses, or dates of birth/diagnosis) was collected. Because no contact information was available, reminders could not be sent.

Ethical considerations

Although participation was anonymous, clarification was sought from the ethics committees in participating countries regarding the need for ethical approval, which was subsequently obtained prior to data collection. This was not required in countries where recruitment was conducted exclusively through survivor organizations, as these organizations did not require ethical approval for participant recruitment.

Data collection

Data collection in each country started once the translations of all study documents and the questionnaire set were completed. Consequently, the start dates varied by country, with the earliest being August 8, 2024. The survey closed on December 1, 2024. Detailed study procedures per country, including start dates, recruitment strategies, and ethical approvals, are provided in **Appendix B**.

Translation of questionnaire

The study questionnaire was available in 15 languages (Catalan, Croatian, Dutch, English, Finnish, French, German, Hungarian, Italian, Norwegian, Romanian, Serbian, Slovenian, Spanish, and Swedish), and took approximately 15–20 minutes to complete. The CCSS-NAQ was translated in 15 languages using DeepL Translate (DeepL SE, Cologne, Germany) and subsequently verified for accuracy by partners fluent in the respective languages, while official translations were available for most languages for the PAM® (13 of 15 languages) and PROMIS measures (11 of 15). If no official translation was available in a participant's language, the respective questionnaire was not administered.

APPENDIX B e-QuoL Needs Study - Information Per Country

No.	Country	Mailing lists	Associations	Social media	Personal contact	Other recruitment	Ethical approval If approved: data of approval and reference number	Start date recruitment
1	Belgium	x	x		x		Requested - Not necessary	08.08.2024
2	Bosnia and Herzegovina	x	x	x	x		Approved on the 20.03.2024 (ref no: 01-19- 122-2/24)	08.08.2024
3	Croatia		x		x	x	Approved on the 17.07.2024 (ref no: 01-23/31- 5-24)	08.08.2024
4	Finland	x	x	x	x	x	Approved on the 26.09.2024 (ref no: T2490/2023)	01.10.2024
5	France	X	x	x	x	x	Requested – Not necessary	08.08.2024
6	Germany	x	x	x		x	Approved on the 14.08.2024 (ref. no: 24- 12037-BO)	16.08.2024
7	Hungary	x	x	x	x	x	Approved on the 3.07.2024	08.08.2024

							(ref. no: BM/17658-1/2024)	
8	Ireland	x					Not necessary	12.08.2024
9	Italy	x	x	x	x		Approved on the 9.09.2024 (ref. no: 300/2024-DB id 14011)	30.10.2024
10	Netherlands			x	x		Recruitment through patient/parents' association only	08.08.2024
11	Norway	x		x			Requested – Not necessary	16.10.2024
12	Romania	x	x	x			Recruitment through patient/parents' association only	12.08.2024
13	Slovenia		x	x	x		Approved on the 30.07.2024 (ref. no: 0120-314/2024-2711-5)	08.08.2024
14	Spain	x	x	x	x		Approved on the 30.09.2024 (ref. no: Reg. HCB/2024/0682)	30.09.2024
15	Switzerland	x	x	x		x	Requested – Not necessary	08.08.2024

APPENDIX C Prevalence of Information and Support Needs on the Item Level (per domain)

Psycho-emotional

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Psycho-emotional													
1. Help dealing with worry	568	111	19.5	124	21.8	105	18.5	150	26.4	78	13.7	1.92	0.74
2. Help dealing with uncertainty about future	568	113	19.9	90	15.8	105	18.5	153	26.9	107	18.8	2.01	0.76
3. Help dealing with anxiety	568	135	23.8	82	14.4	108	19.0	125	22.0	118	20.8	2.03	0.80
4. Help with reducing stress in life	569	87	15.3	91	16.0	132	23.2	141	24.8	118	20.7	1.96	0.80
5. Help dealing with feeling down or depressed	568	151	26.6	96	16.9	106	18.7	120	21.1	95	16.7	1.97	0.79
6. Help dealing with feeling very nervous, afraid, or tense	569	147	25.8	90	15.8	99	17.4	134	23.6	99	17.4	2.00	0.77
7. Help feeling calm and peaceful	569	151	26.5	101	17.8	114	20.0	124	21.8	79	13.9	1.89	0.77
8. Help maintaining a positive outlook	569	163	28.6	101	17.8	112	19.7	110	19.3	83	14.6	1.90	0.80
9. Help dealing with fears about physical disability	569	189	33.2	69	12.1	112	19.7	104	18.3	95	16.7	1.95	0.82
10. Help dealing with feeling angry	568	222	39.1	91	16.0	108	19.0	92	16.2	55	9.7	1.79	0.77
11. Help with loss of control over emotions	568	194	34.2	82	14.4	118	20.8	105	18.5	69	12.1	1.83	0.78
12. Help dealing with fears about pain	568	224	39.4	88	15.5	105	18.5	80	14.1	71	12.5	1.87	0.82
13. Help feeling in control of my situation	564	173	30.7	97	17.2	115	20.4	100	17.7	79	14.0	1.88	0.80
14. Help finding meaning in this experience	566	198	35.0	114	20.1	101	17.8	69	12.2	84	14.8	1.93	0.85
15. Help dealing with changes to my usual routine	569	186	32.7	102	17.9	114	20.0	90	15.8	77	13.5	1.87	0.82
16. Help making the most out of my time	567	211	37.2	84	14.8	108	19.0	96	16.9	68	12.0	1.85	0.79
17. Help dealing with feeling bored or useless	569	245	43.1	84	14.8	86	15.1	90	15.8	64	11.2	1.91	0.79

Health system concern

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Health system concerns													
1. Information about important aspects of my after-cancer care	530	63	11.9	149	28.1	93	17.5	108	20.4	117	22.1	2.08	0.81
2. My doctors to talk to each other to coordinate my care	532	98	18.4	153	28.8	70	13.2	94	17.7	117	22.0	2.17	0.80
3. One health care provider with whom I could talk about my health	529	78	14.7	144	27.2	95	18.0	100	18.9	112	21.2	2.06	0.82
4. Help to know how to give input to my medical team in order to manage my health	529	128	24.2	133	25.1	101	19.1	75	14.2	92	17.4	1.97	0.85
5. Information about whom to call for help	530	116	21.9	135	25.5	86	16.2	97	18.3	96	18.1	2.04	0.81
6. Choices about when to go in for check-ups	532	115	21.6	179	33.6	81	15.2	71	13.3	86	16.2	2.02	0.84
7. My complaints about my care heard and addressed	530	176	33.2	120	22.6	93	17.5	53	10.0	88	16.6	1.98	0.88
8. To be treated like a person not just another case	529	131	24.8	148	28.0	61	11.5	72	13.6	117	22.1	2.22	0.82
9. Help finding access to professional counseling	529	128	24.2	131	24.8	81	15.3	80	15.1	109	20.6	2.10	0.83
10. Information about support groups in my area	530	175	33.0	111	20.9	85	16.0	81	15.3	78	14.7	1.97	0.82

Cancer-related health information

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Cancer-related health information													
1. Information about the late effects of my cancer therapy	514	43	8.4	119	23.2	71	13.8	121	23.5	160	31.1	2.25	0.77
2. Information about how cancer affected my body	513	33	6.4	104	20.3	80	15.6	124	24.2	172	33.5	2.24	0.78
3. Information about which organ systems may have been affected by my cancer treatment	514	43	8.4	102	19.8	82	16.0	114	22.2	173	33.7	2.25	0.79
4. Information about specific diseases that can result from cancer therapy	513	43	8.4	80	15.6	78	15.2	126	24.6	186	36.3	2.28	0.78
5. Information about what I can do to reduce my chances of developing late effects	515	52	10.1	77	15.0	81	15.7	103	20.0	202	39.2	2.31	0.80
6. Information about how cancer will affect my life	513	64	12.5	84	16.4	82	16.0	109	21.2	174	33.9	2.25	0.80
7. Information about cancer recurrence	514	63	12.3	117	22.8	84	16.3	88	17.1	162	31.5	2.23	0.83
8. Information about my treatments or medications received during the cancer treatment	515	62	12.0	140	27.2	82	15.9	92	17.9	139	27.0	2.18	0.82
9. Information about what symptoms to report to the doctor or nurse	513	78	15.2	117	22.8	77	15.0	107	20.9	134	26.1	2.18	0.80
10. Information about what causes cancer	515	96	18.6	106	20.6	87	16.9	86	16.7	140	27.2	2.17	0.84
11. Information about my test results as soon as possible	515	103	20.0	152	29.5	58	11.3	68	13.2	134	26.0	2.29	0.81

General health

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
General health													
1. Help with feeling tired	496	136	27.4	62	12.5	105	21.2	104	21.0	89	17.9	1.95	0.81
2. Help with lack of pep (energy/vitality)	498	130	26.1	50	10.0	112	22.5	118	23.7	88	17.7	1.92	0.79
3. Help improving overall health	497	108	21.7	95	19.1	92	18.5	118	23.7	84	16.9	1.97	0.77
4. Help with managing late effects of cancer	495	93	18.8	79	16.0	97	19.6	96	19.4	130	26.3	2.10	0.83
5. Help feeling as healthy as other people	498	126	25.3	84	16.9	90	18.1	94	18.9	104	20.9	2.05	0.82
6. Help maintaining overall health	498	105	21.1	109	21.9	91	18.3	97	19.5	96	19.3	2.02	0.81
7. Help with feeling unwell a lot of the time	496	180	36.3	61	12.3	85	17.1	85	17.1	85	17.1	2.00	0.82
8. Help accomplishing what I would like to because of physical health	495	179	36.2	62	12.5	94	19.0	87	17.6	73	14.7	1.92	0.81
9. Help performing work or other daily activities because of physical health	496	210	42.3	67	13.5	84	16.9	72	14.5	63	12.7	1.90	0.82
10. Help accomplishing what I would like to because of emotional health	497	169	34.0	63	12.7	78	15.7	98	19.7	89	17.9	2.04	0.79
11. Help continuing usual hobbies or sports	494	199	40.3	70	14.2	88	17.8	70	14.2	67	13.6	1.91	0.83
12. Help doing the things that I used to do	496	226	45.6	71	14.3	70	14.1	73	14.7	56	11.3	1.93	0.79
13. Help performing work or other daily activities because of emotional problems	497	214	43.1	53	10.7	94	18.9	68	13.7	68	13.7	1.89	0.83
14. Help with work around the home	497	275	55.3	54	10.9	71	14.3	54	10.9	43	8.7	1.83	0.81
15. Help climbing one flight of stairs	494	343	69.4	47	9.5	49	9.9	29	5.9	26	5.3	1.78	0.82
16. Help with preparing meals or doing light housework or yard work	496	317	63.9	56	11.3	65	13.1	28	5.6	30	6.0	1.72	0.83

Survivor care and support

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Survivor care and support													
1. To be able to see the specialists I need/want to see	472	82	17.4	122	25.8	86	18.2	85	18.0	97	20.6	2.04	0.83
2. My physician to help me understand how to reduce my late effects risks	472	75	15.9	106	22.5	94	19.9	90	19.1	107	22.7	2.04	0.83
3. To know whom to call if I have questions	471	68	14.4	124	26.3	82	17.4	91	19.3	106	22.5	2.09	0.82
4. Health care providers to acknowledge and show sensitivity to my feelings and emotional needs	471	88	18.7	120	25.5	75	15.9	90	19.1	98	20.8	2.09	0.81
5. To have my physician understand my points of view	472	71	15.0	136	28.8	91	19.3	76	16.1	98	20.8	2.03	0.85
6. My physician to answer my questions fully and carefully	471	61	13.0	149	31.6	71	15.1	78	16.6	112	23.8	2.16	0.82
7. To know how to ask my physician to provide me with choices/options	470	104	22.1	123	26.2	85	18.1	73	15.5	85	18.1	2.00	0.84
8. Reassurance by medical staff that the way I feel is normal	470	117	24.9	123	26.2	77	16.4	60	12.8	93	19.8	2.07	0.86
9. To know that the medical staff is being honest	472	91	19.3	154	32.6	47	10.0	66	14.0	114	24.2	2.30	0.79
10. To share my feelings with my physician	470	122	26.0	122	26.0	77	16.4	70	14.9	79	16.8	2.01	0.83
11. My physician to care about me as a person	471	71	15.1	161	34.2	61	13.0	80	17.0	98	20.8	2.15	0.80
12. My physician to encourage me to ask questions	472	96	20.3	138	29.2	67	14.2	80	16.9	91	19.3	2.10	0.81
13. My physician to listen to how I would like to do things	468	97	20.7	149	31.8	69	14.7	71	15.2	82	17.5	2.06	0.82
14. To secure more timely clinic appointments	471	109	23.1	115	24.4	69	14.6	62	13.2	116	24.6	2.19	0.85
15. Someone to respond to my requests for medical help	470	101	21.5	142	30.2	60	12.8	69	14.7	98	20.9	2.17	0.82
16. More say in decisions about my medical treatment	469	148	31.6	118	25.2	69	14.7	61	13.0	73	15.6	2.02	0.84
17. My physician to understand how I see things before suggesting a new way to do things	471	131	27.8	121	25.7	68	14.4	77	16.3	74	15.7	2.03	0.81
18. To have more trust in my physician	471	138	29.3	136	28.9	68	14.4	54	11.5	75	15.9	2.04	0.85

19. My physician to have more confidence in my ability to make changes that are good for my health	468	164	35.0	132	28.2	62	13.2	49	10.5	61	13.0	1.99	0.85
20. My physician to be more accepting of me	468	169	36.1	126	26.9	62	13.2	50	10.7	61	13.0	1.99	0.85

Surveillance

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Surveillance													
1. Information about what screening tests I need based on my cancer (risk of recurrence)	458	52	11.4	126	27.5	73	15.9	84	18.3	123	26.9	2.18	0.82
2. Information about which tests will help detect late effects of treatment	458	44	9.6	85	18.6	81	17.7	93	20.3	155	33.8	2.22	0.82
3. Information about why screening tests need to be performed	457	71	15.5	125	27.4	79	17.3	71	15.5	111	24.3	2.12	0.85
4. Information about how screening tests are performed	455	75	16.5	111	24.4	84	18.5	86	18.9	99	21.8	2.06	0.82
5. Information about how I will feel during screening tests	455	104	22.9	113	24.8	83	18.2	67	14.7	88	19.3	2.02	0.85
6. Information on how to prepare for screening tests	456	96	21.1	116	25.4	94	20.6	65	14.3	85	18.6	1.96	0.86
7. Information about how I will feel after screening tests	458	121	26.4	101	22.1	85	18.6	73	15.9	78	17.0	1.97	0.83
8. Help with responsibilities so that I can participate in the recommended health screenings	454	119	26.2	96	21.1	80	17.6	65	14.3	94	20.7	2.06	0.85
9. Realistic information about how much time screening tests will take	455	116	25.5	98	21.5	83	18.2	69	15.2	89	19.6	2.02	0.85

Coping and life perspective

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Coping and life perspective													
1. Emotional support	449	76	16.9	101	22.5	76	16.9	88	19.6	108	24.1	2.12	0.82
2. Opportunity to talk with someone who understands/has been through a similar experience	451	79	17.5	99	22.0	81	18.0	91	20.2	101	22.4	2.07	0.81
3. To talk to other people about cancer	452	81	17.9	129	28.5	80	17.7	73	16.2	89	19.7	2.04	0.84
4. Help coping with unpredictability of future	450	102	22.7	68	15.1	82	18.2	83	18.4	115	25.6	2.12	0.83
5. Help with body image issues	452	148	32.7	52	11.5	93	20.6	68	15.0	91	20.1	1.99	0.86
6. Help adjusting to changes in my body	451	147	32.6	63	14.0	78	17.3	65	14.4	98	21.7	2.08	0.85
7. Making decisions about my life	449	144	32.1	87	19.4	73	16.3	66	14.7	79	17.6	2.03	0.84
8. Help dealing with feeling loss of control over life	449	167	37.2	51	11.4	70	15.6	63	14.0	98	21.8	2.12	0.85
9. Help making sense/meaning of my illness	451	170	37.7	77	17.1	66	14.6	57	12.6	81	18.0	2.07	0.85
10. Help moving on with my life	451	175	38.8	78	17.3	55	12.2	61	13.5	82	18.2	2.14	0.82
11. Help trying to make my life count	452	175	38.7	79	17.5	56	12.4	59	13.1	83	18.4	2.14	0.83
12. Help dealing with changes in how I feel as a man or woman	445	196	44.0	60	13.5	59	13.3	55	12.4	75	16.9	2.08	0.84

Fiscal concerns

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Fiscal concerns													
1. Insurance coverage for my other medical expenses	441	153	34.7	80	18.1	56	12.7	51	11.6	101	22.9	2.22	0.84
2. Insurance coverage for my medications	441	163	37.0	92	20.9	47	10.7	43	9.8	96	21.8	2.26	0.84
3. Help understanding my health insurance coverage	441	162	36.7	69	15.6	62	14.1	57	12.9	91	20.6	2.14	0.84
4. Help with concerns about my financial situation	441	181	41.0	63	14.3	75	17.0	54	12.2	68	15.4	1.96	0.85
5. Help paying for physician or hospital costs	440	196	44.5	73	16.6	62	14.1	45	10.2	64	14.5	2.01	0.86
6. Help paying for medical treatments	442	193	43.7	75	17.0	53	12.0	59	13.3	62	14.0	2.05	0.81
7. Help paying for prescription medications	441	204	46.3	75	17.0	53	12.0	44	10.0	65	14.7	2.07	0.85
8. Help paying for medical screenings	439	201	45.8	78	17.8	47	10.7	45	10.3	68	15.5	2.13	0.84
9. Help meeting my basic living expenses	440	223	50.7	68	15.5	52	11.8	43	9.8	54	12.3	2.01	0.85
10. Help with payments for care denied by my insurance carrier	443	235	53.0	40	9.0	58	13.1	42	9.5	68	15.3	2.06	0.87
11. Help dealing with extra expenses because of cancer	443	202	45.6	43	9.7	65	14.7	52	11.7	81	18.3	2.08	0.86
12. Help completing insurance forms	443	232	52.4	55	12.4	66	14.9	38	8.6	52	11.7	1.91	0.87
13. Help dealing with reduced income because of cancer	443	226	51.0	37	8.4	46	10.4	62	14.0	72	16.3	2.14	0.80
14. Assistance with disability or social security	441	217	49.2	58	13.2	46	10.4	34	7.7	86	19.5	2.24	0.86
15. Help with being unable to work because of pain	443	243	54.9	41	9.3	41	9.3	43	9.7	75	16.9	2.21	0.83
16. Help with being unable to work because of chronic fatigue	442	218	49.3	35	7.9	56	12.7	54	12.2	79	17.9	2.12	0.84
17. Transportation to and from medical appointments/screenings	443	240	54.2	55	12.4	52	11.7	39	8.8	57	12.9	2.03	0.86
18. Help keeping my job	443	242	54.6	49	11.1	57	12.9	30	6.8	65	14.7	2.05	0.90
19. Help with difficulty working	442	215	48.6	41	9.3	62	14.0	52	11.8	72	16.3	2.05	0.85
20. Help making the same salary	441	249	56.5	41	9.3	40	9.1	39	8.8	72	16.3	2.21	0.84
21. Help with at-work concerns	440	248	56.4	36	8.2	49	11.1	48	10.9	59	13.4	2.06	0.83
22. More accessible parking at health care center	442	245	55.4	40	9.0	48	10.9	43	9.7	66	14.9	2.11	0.85
23. Transportation to do errands and go shopping	442	303	68.6	43	9.7	37	8.4	29	6.6	30	6.8	1.93	0.84
24. Transportation to school or work	443	305	68.8	46	10.4	37	8.4	30	6.8	25	5.6	1.87	0.81

25. Transportation for work or household activities	438	298	68.0	50	11.4	33	7.5	29	6.6	28	6.4	1.94	0.83
---	-----	-----	------	----	------	----	-----	----	-----	----	-----	------	------

Relationships

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Relationships													
1. Someone that I could really talk to	433	73	16.9	140	32.3	65	15.0	64	14.8	91	21.0	2.12	0.84
2. Help with feeling alone	432	120	27.8	101	23.4	67	15.5	67	15.5	77	17.8	2.05	0.83
3. Others to acknowledge the impact of cancer on my life	432	97	22.5	88	20.4	72	16.7	67	15.5	108	25.0	2.15	0.84
4. Help dealing with changes in other people's attitudes/behavior toward me	431	151	35.0	76	17.6	70	16.2	63	14.6	71	16.5	2.00	0.83
5. Help with difficulties with my family or spouse	432	200	46.3	66	15.3	54	12.5	54	12.5	58	13.4	2.02	0.82
6. Help engaging in social activities because of physical health/emotional problems	433	181	41.8	65	15.0	56	12.9	67	15.5	64	14.8	2.04	0.80
7. Help dealing with increased emotional problems at home	433	190	43.9	61	14.1	75	17.3	53	12.2	54	12.5	1.88	0.84
8. Help dealing with increased tension or arguments at home	433	223	51.5	52	12.0	61	14.1	45	10.4	52	12.0	1.94	0.85
9. Help talking about my health with my family and friends	432	189	43.8	76	17.6	68	15.7	43	10.0	56	13.0	1.93	0.86
10. Help communicating with friends/relatives	431	198	45.9	74	17.2	61	14.2	41	9.5	57	13.2	1.97	0.86
11. Help dealing with difficulty in interacting with friends/relatives	427	202	47.3	68	15.9	58	13.6	47	11.0	52	12.2	1.96	0.84
12. To be more reassured by my relatives	430	220	51.2	76	17.7	55	12.8	30	7.0	49	11.4	1.96	0.88
13. To feel more useful within my family	431	216	50.1	79	18.3	46	10.7	42	9.7	48	11.1	2.01	0.83
14. Help interacting with partner/spouse	429	250	58.3	58	13.5	39	9.1	41	9.6	41	9.6	2.02	0.82
15. Help taking part in community activities	431	231	53.6	70	16.2	61	14.2	36	8.4	33	7.7	1.78	0.83
16. Help interacting with children	428	282	65.9	60	14.0	35	8.2	18	4.2	33	7.7	1.98	0.89

Sexuality

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Sexuality													
1. Help with changes in sexual feelings (libido)	415	211	50.8	46	11.1	64	15.4	39	9.4	55	13.3	1.94	0.87
2. Help with changes in sexual relationships	415	224	54.0	50	12.0	61	14.7	36	8.7	44	10.6	1.88	0.86
3. Information about sexual relationships	417	227	54.4	51	12.2	52	12.5	41	9.8	46	11.0	1.96	0.84
4. Counseling related to sexuality or intimacy	417	222	53.2	39	9.4	55	13.2	49	11.8	52	12.5	1.98	0.83
5. Help with sexual dysfunction	415	235	56.6	34	8.2	56	13.5	40	9.6	50	12.0	1.96	0.85
6. Information about how cancer treatment may affect my sexual health	418	144	34.4	48	11.5	66	15.8	75	17.9	85	20.3	2.08	0.81
7. Help dealing with concerns about my ability to participate in sexual activity	415	215	51.8	33	8.0	54	13.0	50	12.0	63	15.2	2.05	0.84

Services

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Services													
1. Infertility treatment/services	421	166	39.4	61	14.5	48	11.4	54	12.8	92	21.9	2.23	0.82
2. Adoption services	424	255	60.1	24	5.7	30	7.1	43	10.1	72	17.0	2.29	0.79
3. Complementary/alternative health care services	423	207	48.9	34	8.0	50	11.8	60	14.2	72	17.0	2.12	0.81
4. Information about camps, retreats	422	211	50.0	43	10.2	70	16.6	39	9.2	59	14.0	1.93	0.88
5. Child care	422	317	75.1	32	7.6	24	5.7	14	3.3	35	8.3	2.15	0.89
6. Legal services	420	253	60.2	26	6.2	55	13.1	33	7.9	53	12.6	1.99	0.88
7. Alcohol or drug abuse counseling	424	336	79.2	24	5.7	28	6.6	14	3.3	22	5.2	1.91	0.89
8. Internet websites for cancer survivors	423	157	37.1	64	15.1	69	16.3	62	14.7	71	16.8	2.01	0.83
9. Information about my health during pregnancy (for women only)	421	132	31.4	20	4.8	34	8.1	37	8.8	72	17.1	2.27	0.82
10. Chance of my child developing cancer	421	143	34.0	29	6.9	52	12.4	54	12.8	143	34.0	2.37	0.81

Spirituality

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Spirituality													
1. Religious or spiritual counseling	421	290	68.9	48	11.4	40	9.5	20	4.8	23	5.5	1.80	0.85
2. Help exploring spiritual beliefs	420	302	71.9	41	9.8	43	10.2	12	2.9	22	5.2	1.73	0.88
3. Help with changes to beliefs	420	315	75.0	36	8.6	30	7.1	16	3.8	23	5.5	1.90	0.88
4. Help with difficulties in keeping confidence in God or religion	417	307	73.6	40	9.6	42	10.1	11	2.6	17	4.1	1.64	0.85

Nutrition

Domain/ Item	Total N	No need		Need satisfied		Low need		Moderate need		High need		Mean need (if need present)	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	mean	SD
Nutrition													
1. Information about a healthy diet	422	113	26.8	113	26.8	69	16.4	54	12.8	73	17.3	2.02	0.85
2. Information about how many servings of fruits and vegetables to eat per day	422	150	35.5	119	28.2	62	14.7	39	9.2	52	12.3	1.93	0.86
3. Information about which fats to cut down or out	422	133	31.5	103	24.4	70	16.6	51	12.1	65	15.4	1.97	0.85
4. Information about which foods are high or low in added sugar	421	134	31.8	107	25.4	69	16.4	47	11.2	64	15.2	1.97	0.86
5. Information about the different types of fiber and their benefits	421	126	29.9	101	24.0	76	18.1	53	12.6	65	15.4	1.94	0.85
6. Information about which foods can reduce or increase chances of getting cancer	422	101	23.9	68	16.1	67	15.9	75	17.8	111	26.3	2.17	0.82
7. Information about supplements such as vitamins, minerals, herbal products, soy, and plant extracts	419	117	27.9	82	19.6	69	16.5	56	13.4	95	22.7	2.12	0.86

APPENDIX D Prevalence of Information and Support Needs by European Region

Domain	European region	≥50% items completed	Any need		Average low need ^a		Average moderate need ^a		Average high need ^a		Mean need level (if any need)
		N	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean, SD
Psycho-emotional	Total	569	495	87.0	325	57.1	125	22.0	45	7.9	1.18 ± 0.84
	Northern	119	100	84.0	80	67.2	19	16.0	1	0.8	0.86 ± 0.67
	Western	161	152	94.4	104	64.6	37	23.0	11	6.8	1.12 ± 0.79
	Eastern	71	62	87.3	35	49.3	18	25.4	9	12.7	1.39 ± 0.94
	Southern	218	181	83.0	106	48.6	51	23.4	24	11.0	1.33 ± 0.87
Health system concerns	Total	532	444	83.5	272	51.1	109	20.5	63	11.8	1.26 ± 0.90
	Northern	114	98	86.0	73	64.0	18	15.8	7	6.1	0.97 ± 0.78
	Western	149	138	92.6	86	57.7	38	25.5	14	9.4	1.28 ± 0.85
	Eastern	63	48	76.2	23	36.5	10	15.9	15	23.8	1.68 ± 0.93
	Southern	206	160	77.7	90	43.7	43	20.9	27	13.1	1.28 ± 0.94
Cancer-related health information	Total	515	465	90.3	202	39.2	143	27.8	120	23.3	1.66 ± 0.94
	Northern	110	105	95.5	64	58.2	29	26.4	12	10.9	1.32 ± 0.85
	Western	144	136	94.4	54	37.5	52	36.1	30	20.8	1.73 ± 0.82
	Eastern	61	50	82.0	16	26.2	15	24.6	19	31.1	1.96 ± 0.95
	Southern	200	174	87.0	68	34.0	47	23.5	59	29.5	1.72 ± 1.02
General health	Total	498	413	82.9	272	54.6	101	20.3	40	8.0	1.14 ± 0.84
	Northern	110	93	84.6	70	63.6	20	18.2	3	2.7	0.82 ± 0.71
	Western	139	121	87.1	82	59.0	26	18.7	13	9.4	1.19 ± 0.83
	Eastern	59	43	72.9	21	35.6	17	28.8	5	8.5	1.42 ± 0.88
	Southern	190	156	82.1	99	52.1	38	20.0	19	10.0	1.22 ± 0.85
Survivor care and support	Total	472	392	83.1	241	51.1	86	18.2	65	13.8	1.25 ± 0.94
	Northern	104	89	85.6	67	64.4	15	14.4	7	6.7	0.94 ± 0.83
	Western	128	116	90.6	77	60.2	25	19.5	14	10.9	1.18 ± 0.89
	Eastern	55	44	80.0	17	30.9	15	27.3	12	21.8	1.65 ± 0.97
	Southern	185	143	77.3	80	43.2	31	16.8	32	17.3	1.37 ± 0.98

Domain	European region	≥ 50% items completed	Any need		Average low need ^a		Average moderate need ^a		Average high need ^a		Mean need level (if any need)
		N	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean, SD
Surveillance	Total	458	372	81.2	200	43.7	103	22.5	69	15.1	1.45 ± 0.93
	Northern	103	86	83.5	64	62.1	17	16.5	5	4.9	1.03 ± 0.80
	Western	124	108	87.1	62	50.0	33	26.6	13	10.5	1.32 ± 0.85
	Eastern	51	41	80.4	17	33.3	9	17.7	15	29.4	1.84 ± 0.98
	Southern	180	137	76.1	57	31.7	44	24.4	36	20.0	1.72 ± 0.94
Coping	Total	452	370	81.9	225	49.8	82	18.1	63	13.9	1.32 ± 0.95
	Northern	101	83	82.2	66	65.3	12	11.9	5	5.0	0.92 ± 0.80
	Western	123	109	88.6	63	51.2	28	22.8	18	14.6	1.34 ± 0.91
	Eastern	50	40	80.0	18	36.0	10	20.0	12	24.0	1.65 ± 0.98
	Southern	178	138	77.5	78	43.8	32	18.0	28	15.7	1.44 ± 0.98
Fiscal concerns	Total	443	331	74.7	238	53.7	59	13.3	34	7.7	1.03 ± 0.89
	Northern	100	59	59.0	51	51.0	6	6.0	2	2.0	0.64 ± 0.68
	Western	120	96	80.0	77	64.2	15	12.5	4	3.3	0.85 ± 0.77
	Eastern	47	40	85.1	24	51.1	7	14.9	9	19.1	1.34 ± 1.03
	Southern	176	136	77.3	86	48.9	31	17.6	19	10.8	1.23 ± 0.92
Relationships	Total	433	321	74.1	226	52.2	66	15.2	29	6.7	1.05 ± 0.86
	Northern	96	70	72.9	61	63.5	9	9.4	0	0.0	0.65 ± 0.59
	Western	120	95	79.2	68	56.7	24	20.0	3	2.5	1.00 ± 0.79
	Eastern	44	29	65.9	18	40.9	6	13.6	5	11.4	1.44 ± 0.87
	Southern	173	127	73.4	79	45.7	27	15.6	21	12.1	1.21 ± 0.96
Sexuality	Total	418	259	62.0	170	40.7	51	12.2	38	9.1	1.25 ± 0.90
	Northern	95	49	51.6	34	35.8	8	8.4	7	7.4	1.12 ± 0.89
	Western	116	77	66.4	48	41.4	19	16.4	10	8.6	1.26 ± 0.84
	Eastern	45	35	77.8	21	46.7	8	17.8	6	13.3	1.37 ± 0.98
	Southern	162	98	60.5	67	41.4	16	9.9	15	9.3	1.26 ± 0.92

Domain	European region	≥ 50% items completed	Any need		Average low need ^a		Average moderate need ^a		Average high need ^a		Mean need level (if any need)
		N	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Mean, SD
Services	Total	424	349	82.3	267	63.0	60	14.2	22	5.2	0.99 ± 0.77
	Northern	95	78	82.1	74	77.9	4	4.2	0	0.0	0.65 ± 0.46
	Western	116	104	89.7	86	74.1	16	13.8	2	1.7	0.87 ± 0.65
	Eastern	44	34	77.3	19	43.2	7	15.9	8	18.2	1.48 ± 1.01
	Southern	169	133	78.7	88	52.1	33	19.5	12	7.1	1.15 ± 0.84
Nutrition	Total	422	279	66.1	159	37.7	63	14.9	57	13.5	1.44 ± 0.96
	Northern	96	45	46.9	34	35.4	8	8.3	3	3.1	0.92 ± 0.83
	Western	116	83	71.6	54	46.6	21	18.1	8	6.9	1.22 ± 0.82
	Eastern	43	36	83.7	18	41.9	6	14.0	12	27.9	1.76 ± 0.97
	Southern	167	115	68.9	53	31.7	28	16.8	34	20.4	1.70 ± 0.98
Spirituality	Total	421	115	27.3	81	19.2	16	3.8	18	4.3	1.16 ± 0.90
	Northern	96	16	16.7	12	12.5	3	3.1	1	1.0	0.92 ± 0.68
	Western	115	25	21.7	22	19.1	2	1.7	1	0.9	0.70 ± 0.60
	Eastern	44	20	45.5	12	27.3	3	6.8	5	11.4	1.51 ± 1.00
	Southern	166	54	32.5	35	21.1	8	4.8	11	6.6	1.31 ± 0.95

^a Among participants who reported at least one need within a domain, we calculated the average domain-level need. Item responses were recoded as 0 = no or met (satisfied) need, 1 = low, 2 = moderate, and 3 = high need. The mean score across all completed items within a domain was then calculated. Domain-level needs were categorized as no (0), low (>0-<1.5), moderate (≥1.5-<2.5), or high (≥2.5-3).

APPENDIX E Separate Models Examining the Associations of Information and Support Needs (Any vs. No Need) with Patient Activation (PAM®) and Mental and Physical Global Health (PROMIS)

Outcomes	PAM® (low vs. high) OR (90% CI)	PROMIS global mental T- score B (90% CI)	PROMIS global physical T- score B (90% CI)
Predictors			
Information needs (any vs. no need)			
Psycho-emotional	0.50 (0.28; 0.90)*	-10.32 (-12.65; -7.98)***	-7.42 (-9.89; -4.96)***
Health system concerns	0.42 (0.24; 0.74)*	-7.05 (-9.49; -4.61)***	-6.62 (-9.09; -4.14)***
Cancer-related health information	0.33 (0.16; 0.69)*	-6.68 (-9.83; -3.52)***	-5.39 (-8.59; -2.19)**
General health	0.45 (0.27; 0.76)*	-10.22 (-12.35; -8.09)***	-9.26 (-11.45; -7.06)***
Survivor care and support	0.39 (0.22; 0.68)**	-7.28 (-9.61; -4.95)***	-6.75 (-9.12; -4.38)***
Surveillance	0.45 (0.27; 0.75)**	-6.92 (-9.08; -4.75)***	-5.02 (-7.26; -2.78)***
Coping	0.42 (0.25; 0.68)**	-9.41 (-11.56; -7.25)***	-7.00 (-9.26; -4.74)***
Fiscal concerns	0.48 (0.31; 0.74)**	-5.68 (-7.58; -3.78)***	-6.58 (-8.47; -4.69)***
Relationships	0.31 (0.20; 0.49)***	-8.25 (-10.06; -6.43)***	-5.64 (-7.56; -3.71)***
Sexuality	0.61 (0.42; 0.90)*	-5.50 (-7.21; -3.79)***	-4.48 (-6.24; -2.72)***
Services	0.49 (0.29; 0.82)*	-6.55 (-8.82; -4.28)***	-5.74 (-8.05; -3.42)***
Nutrition	0.40 (0.27; 0.61)***	-5.46 (-7.24; -3.69)***	-4.31 (-6.13; -2.48)***
Spirituality	0.73 (0.47; 1.12)	-3.81 (-5.81; -1.81)**	-4.37 (-6.38; -2.35)***

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.
Significant results are presented in **bold**.

****Notes.

Associations are adjusted for gender, age at study, European region, education level, time since diagnosis, and type of diagnosis.

Analyses are conducted for each domain of information and support needs separately.

No significant association was found between the spirituality domain and patient activation (p > 0.10).